

Characteristics of the Relationship between Adolescents and Parents

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Annotation:

This article examines the issues of changing the relationship of the personality of a teenager and parents, Consider the views of different authors on the relationship between adolescents and parents. And also recommendations are given to parents on the correct structure of relations, with the child - adolescent, on the correction of relationships and on the prevention of problems arising in the internal family relations.

Keywords: the relationship of a teenager with parents, emotional dependence, emotional warmth, old friend, the desire for independence, emotional connection, crisis period, family climate, psychological barrier, hyperprotection, hypoprotection, emotional rejection.

The general pattern and biggest problem in adolescence is the rebuilding of relationships with parents, that is, the transition from childhood dependence, dependence, to relationships based on mutual trust, respect, and, if relative, continuously growing equality. In many families, such restructuring is difficult and perceived by parents as disobedience. But let's look at this situation from the perspective of the emerging individual.

According to different children, fathers and mothers are for them: a person of emotional warmth and support, a person of governing power, a punisher and a rewarder, an example for imitation, a model of wisdom and the best qualities in a person, a great friend and adviser, a person who can trust everything. However, the relationship and psychological significance of each of these tasks changes with age.

The child's emotional dependence on their parents is primarily based on their dependence. With the growth of activity and initiative, this dependence begins to bother him in adolescence. A lack of parental love is very bad, but too much is also harmful. It complicates the formation of internal self-

regulation, creates a stable need for care, a quality of character dependence. A parent's over-comfortable "nest" does not prepare a child to fly through the complex adult world.

Mothers who love their child too much are unable to see their child separately from themselves. However, a teenager cannot grow up without breaking off emotional dependence and introducing a new, more complex emotional connection into their relationship with their parents, a more complex system in which the center is not the parent.

Many parents, feeling cold from their children, think that their children have lost love for them, accusing them of ruthlessness. However, after a period of crisis, if they themselves have not spoiled it with improper upbringing, relationships are usually restored at a higher, conscious level.

Adolescence is a period of striving for independence. The success of this period largely depends on how the teenager's separation from the family is progressing, that is, on the construction of relationships between the teenager and the parents, based not on patronage and care, but on cooperation. A parent's job is to help a teenager grow up. If the family is not ready to "release" the teenager, if the teenager and the parents have different views on the rights and independence of the child, then problems arise in the relationship between the teenager and the parents.

The growth of a child's independence limits parental control. A teenager independently spends their time, choosing their friends and methods of recreation. This situation is difficult for parents to accept. The reason is that parents are often unprepared to build a new type of relationship with the teenager, in particular, to expand the teenager's independence and rights. Because human rights change with a change in the status they hold. The teenager remains a student, financially dependent on their parents, and the parents continue to play the role of educators. This is why parents retain their attitude towards a teenager and do not want to change anything.

Teenagers, on the other hand, want to see more of their friends and advisors in their parents. No matter how independent adolescents may be, they need help and life experience, advice from adults. Many of the problems teenagers are unable to discuss with their peers at all: what advice could a person who doesn't have the same life experience give? For many adolescents, it becomes very important for their parents to understand them.

Parents' efforts to control the teenager, to force their views and interests on him, create resistance. Nevertheless, old relationships are replaced by new ones, and who is the initiator of such a change plays an important role in relationships. If the initiator of the relationship change is the parent, it will be possible to avoid serious problems in the relationship with the teenager and manage this process, and if it is the teenager, then conflicts and conflicts are undeniable.

According to psychologist V. Rudenko, three manifestations can arise in the relationship between teenagers and parents:

The first manifestation: the contradictions increase, the conflicts deepen and expand. A teenager develops negative personality traits, such as aggression, lying, and other negative qualities. Relationships with parents lose their significance for a teenager. Parents gradually lose their reputation, their demands, views, and evaluations are denied. To show dissatisfaction with their parents, adolescents avoid classes, begin smoking, befriend children forbidden by their parents, sometimes run away from home, drink alcohol, and begin taking drugs.

The second manifestation: there is a conflict in the family, which only turns into episodic conflicts. Although the parents do not completely change their attitude towards the teenager, but sometimes they give in to his pressure and allow what they have not previously allowed. Therefore, collisions are rare, but the probability of their occurrence remains for a long time.

The third manifestation: parents gradually begin to see in a teenager not a child, but a mature individual, and accordingly, they change their attitude towards him. As a result, conflict situations disappear over time, and problematic communication is replaced by mutual trust and cooperative relationships.

What educational methods should be used to properly build relationships between teenagers and parents? V. Karimova presents various methods of raising children in families:

Hyperprotection is excessive care. Parents devote their time, energy, and attention to raising their children. The upbringing of a child becomes the meaning of a parent's life. All the child's needs and desires are met, and they try not to notice their mistakes. In adolescence, such children want their peers to fulfill their desires, strive for leadership, but they do not have such qualities.

Hyperprotection overcoming care. In this case, it is more important to control each step of the child than to pamper him. There are many limitations, prohibitions (impossible) in a child's life. As an adult, such a child is unable to make independent decisions, irritable about anything, and needs constant control and guidance from others.

Extreme moral responsibility. At the same time, the parents place high demands on the child's age, intellect, and physical abilities, but their wishes and needs are not taken into account.

Emotional denial. Parents tell the child that they are making their lives more difficult, that their lives would have been different without him. Such relationships alienate a child from the family.

Harshness. It's like emotional denial, but harder than that. A child grows up under beatings, insults, and abuse from an early age. By adolescence, children raised in such families may exhibit extreme cruelty towards those who are weaker than themselves.

Hypoprotection. Parents either don't have enough time to take care of their children or leave it to others. In such families, the child is left to their own devices. An atmosphere of indifference prevails in relation to him. Behavior is uncontrollable. Children from such families are more likely to become involved in criminal gangs during their adolescence.

Adolescents are grown-up children. They still need care, attention and love. Many parents love their children and think they are giving their love to their children. Indeed, they are mistaken. Usually, parents are unable to give and show their love to a teenager because they don't know how to do it.

Young children are always hugged and kissed by their parents. But as the child grows up, the number of embraces and kisses decreases, and teenagers are not embraced or kissed by their parents at all. One reason for this is that teenagers avoid this because they are not young children. But they still need their parents' love. Therefore, it is necessary to show love to the teenager without embarrassment.

But it's important to remember that giving a teenager love is not a one-time affair, it's a continuous process. It's not just hugging and kissing. It is necessary to tell the teenager how much they love him, how proud they are of him, how much he has good, and how much it pleases the parents. It is necessary to list some qualities, to praise one or another achievement. A teenager must firmly believe that his parents love him regardless of his current achievements.

There are situations where parents need to show that they understand the teenager. The best way to show that you understand a teenager is to listen attentively. However, in real life, communication between teenagers and parents depends on trying to control their studies and work at home. Sincerely, it is impossible to talk about everything and nothing: urgent tasks, parental fatigue, on the other hand, alienation of the teenager. There may be situations where the "conversation" between a teenager and a parent consists only of criticism of him. A teenager tries to avoid such communication.

Understanding the inner world of another person is possible only when it is respected, when it is perceived as a separate reality. The most common complaint among teenagers is "They can't hear me." Being in a hurry, unable to listen and unwilling to listen, unwillingness to understand what is happening in a teenager's complex world, not trying to look at the problem through the eyes of their daughter or son, a firm belief in their own life experience - all this creates a psychological barrier between parents and growing children.

Overall, constant dissatisfaction and punishment from parents leads to a feeling of alienation in the teenager. He might come to this conclusion: "Am I bad? I'll be even worse!" To prevent this, parents must constantly maintain the teenager's self-esteem.

A study was conducted on adolescents under the guidance of I.S. Kon. Teenagers were asked to assess their various qualities (kindness, sociability, courage, self-confidence, etc.) using a five-point system. After that, they were asked to find out how they would be rated by their parents, friends, and classmates according to the same system. Parents were invited to the school and asked to assess their children and find out how their children would evaluate themselves. It was found that children were more accurate in how they were evaluated by their parents.

Parents were more likely to make mistakes in determining how their children would evaluate themselves. It was difficult for parents to find the self-esteem of their children. They gave more self-esteem in the self-esteem of their children. This situation indicates that parents do not know their child's "I."

It is not difficult for a child to find the evaluation that his parents give him. Because many parents directly tell their children what they think about them. Therefore, it is easy for a teenager to find the assessment his parents give him. Parents, on the other hand, need to evaluate a newly changing and contradictory adolescent "I." A parent's misconception of the son or daughter's "I" image seriously hinders their children's understanding. Parents do not want to understand the change in the inner world of adolescence and adolescence. A good parent knows their child better than anyone else, even the child himself.

A characteristic of all parents is the ability to speak well, but not to hear. It is very important for a teenager to hear it. He will only be able to listen if he can tell his parents what is inside him. Therefore, parents should learn to listen to him, and only then will the teenager begin to listen to their opinion. This achieves two goals: helping the teenager and gaining their trust.

Teenagers want to tell their parents what they are interested in. If they are not listened to, they will stop talking to their parents after a while. If the teenager's words are not interesting to the parents, they should listen to them, keep the conversation going. Teens should feel that their parents are interested in them.

What to do if a teenager does not "hear" his parents? A parent should draw their child's attention to themselves before saying anything, such as asking them to look at themselves. When a teenager's eyes clash with those of their parents, the parents can ask him their question or request. With regular use of this method, the teenager learns to listen.

If a teenager is engaged in any work, he should be warned in advance for no more than five minutes, for example, "I need your help in 2 minutes," "I want to talk to you in a minute."

One must speak slowly and politely. A teenager ignores criticism, commands, advice, and shouts, but polite speech attracts their attention. It is necessary to speak as briefly, softly, and clearly as possible.

A parent may say something in anger and then regret it. In this case, it is necessary to apologize to the teenager and show that he should apologize for his mistake.

Usually, parents consider it normal if their child behaves well, listens to what is said, and do not pay attention to this situation, do not praise or reward the teenager. But rewarding a teenager for good behavior is better than punishing him for disobeying him.

Of course, a teenager is not rewarded for their normal behavior. For example, because he behaved well around the table. But for the slightest change in his behavior, he should be praised. For example, it is necessary to thank a teenager for his trust, even if he does not speak openly for a long time and talks about something insignificant. If he achieves a better result in studying any subject, it is necessary to praise him. Such praise will not fail in the future.

If a teenager's relationship with adults is the worse, he will try to communicate more with his peers, and his dependence on peers will be very high. However, the influence of parents and peers on a teenager is not always opposite, but they can also complement each other.

The importance of parents and peers is different for different areas of activity. Adolescents prefer to spend their free time with their peers. Psychologist T.N. Malkovskaya's research shows that adolescents and young adults want to spend their free time with their peers. Daughters of parents

The boys placed in 4th place, while the boys placed in 6th place. However, when asked: "Who would you ask for advice in a difficult life situation?," their mothers were in the first place, their fathers were in the second place, and their daughters had friends.

In conclusion, it can be said that adolescence is a period rich in both psychological and physiological changes in the individual. During this period, parents need to reconsider their attitude towards their child. If a parent is patient in communication with their teenage child, tries to understand and listen to him, correctly understands and accepts changes in him, makes qualitative changes in their relationship with their child, encourages the teenager more, and takes into account his opinion on some family issues, any conflicts in their relationship with the teenager will be prevented.

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